

ON THE IMPORTANT PROBLEMS OF THE TYPOLOGY OF MODERN TURKISH AND UZBEK STORIES

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Abstract: This thesis talks about the importance of typology and typology of modern languages in modern Turkish and Uzbek stories. Also, theories about the study of common and specific features of languages in linguistic typology, the main methods in linguistic typology are given. The main problems encountered during the typological analysis of Eastern languages and their solutions are presented.

Key words: Turkish and Uzbek stories, typology, diachronic, synchronic, comparative-historical method, morphological, scientific analysis.

Introduction:

When a person hears or learns different languages, he notices that they have similarities in two ways, that is, external similarities and similarities in the grammatical structure of words, the way they are formed, and the way words are connected in a sentence. In the process of dividing languages into types, importance is given to genetic, morphological and structural classification. Regardless of the genetic relationship of languages, linguistic typology studies linguistic facts that bring them closer and further away from each other. In turn, linguistic typology is divided into hybrid and comparative typology. This phenomenon is related to whether the languages are siblings or not.

Modern linguistic literature shows that linguistic typology first began in the West with the works of F. Schlegel. Later, A.V. Shlegel, V. Humboldt, H. Shteintal, A. Shleicher, E. Sepir, V. Skalichka, A. Martine, F. F. Fortunatov, I. I. Meshchaninov, B. Uspensky, Yu. V. Rozhdestvensky, V. N. A study by Yarseva et al. However, when the views of Eastern thinkers on linguistics were studied, a lot of scientific-linguistic information related to linguistic typology was observed in most of their works. In particular, the early forms of comparative-historical linguistics can be seen in the works of Mahmud Kashgari, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, scholars who lived and worked in Central Asia in the 9th-15th centuries. The reason for such a confusing doctrine may be that European scientists were able to get acquainted with the works of these scholars by the end of the 19th century.

Studying the typological theory of languages is a complex process. For this, a linguist needs strong skills and theoretical mastery of several languages. A peculiarity of linguistic typology is that languages belonging to two systems are intermixed at all levels. Specific features of languages and signs that bring them closer together are identified.

Linguistic typology is a branch of linguistics that studies the structural and functional characteristics of languages, regardless of the genetic relationship between them. From a scientific point of view, linguistic typology is a method of research by dividing the approximating and distancing language facts into groups, patterns, and types. It seems that, on the one hand, typology includes general theories, rules and methods of language classification, and on the other hand, it deals with the classification of language system units based on their common features.

The existence of similarities and differences between related and non-related languages, the desire to study and understand the reasons for the occurrence of these aspects led to the emergence of this linguistic typology, which is recognized as a separate field and direction in linguistics. The development of typology in linguistics is effective in mastering related and unrelated languages.

During the years of independence in Uzbekistan, scientists such as A. Abduazizov, J. Boronov, K. Toymetov, M. Iriskulov dealt with issues of typology. Cross-language learning aims to study translation, linguo-philosophical, linguo-didactic and theoretical issues.

Learning a foreign language, including Eastern languages, is a complex linguistic and psychological phenomenon. When learning a foreign language, the native language and the studied language systems collide in the learner's mind. The learner's native language facilitates the acquisition of a new language system or, on the contrary, becomes an obstacle on his way. In linguistics, the first phenomenon, that is, the emergence of ease in the process of comparing a particular language with one's native language, is called facilitation (in English, "facilitate" means "to help, facilitate, contribute"). On the contrary, the fact that the mother tongue hinders the acquisition of the studied language is interference, that is, Latin interference, inter - between - ferens - to carry, transfer) - in linguistics, the result of the influence of one language on another language means, in other words, in written or spoken speech, the norms of one language are expressed in terms of applying them in another language.

The typological study of modern eastern languages with the native language is one of the relatively new fields in linguistics. Therefore, there are many problems that need to be studied in this field. Languages can also be studied cross-culturally for theoretical purposes. In this, the phonetic, morphological, lexical and syntactic levels of languages are systematically studied, their similarities and differences and their reasons are determined. Linguistic typological research focuses on language universals and is the most important part of the field. Linguistic universals are linguistic categories common to all language systems. Linguistic universals, in other words, universalism studies common categories in language. So, universalism is a generalization of language laws.

Comparative typology studies the typology of genetically and typologically similar languages. In this case, the object of research is sister languages, and their commonality, specificity, and similar and different aspects are determined. Cross-typological study of languages is the determination of their similarities and differences, regardless of whether they belong to the same type or not according to the origin and development, structural, semantic and functional status of selected languages. In cross-typological linguistics, similarities and differences between languages do not depend on whether they belong to the same type or not.

So, the typological study of Eastern languages is a somewhat more complicated hybrid process. In this case, the learner of an oriental language should first of all determine the linguistic features of the mother tongue, its unique aspects, as well as the universals of the language from the point of view of general linguistics. As a result of mixing in such a process, the private and general nature of languages is clearly visible. This situation serves to increase the learner's level of conscious mastery.

Conclusion:

Although the expressions of both languages are similar in meaning, the words contained in them are completely incompatible. Such phrases have different local and national colors. Similarity, polysemy, synonymy, and contradictory phenomena are characteristic of expressions of both languages, like all lexical units. According to the research, the words borrowed from the Turkish language and through this language from other languages in the modern Uzbek literary language amount to about 20% according to the latest statistics. Russian international words in the lexicon of our language are used as active words both in scientific and technical literature and in oral speech. It was found that there

are certain differences between native words and words in the Russian language.

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